

**MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 3 PUPILS
USING THE MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING: BASIS
FOR SCHOOL ACTION PLAN IN AN ENHANCED
KAMUSTAHAN PROGRAM**

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Mathematics Performance Of Grade 3 Pupils Using The Modular Distance Learning: Basis For School Action Plan in an Enhanced Kamustahan Program

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Abstract

This action research determines the performance level of Grade 3 pupils in Mathematics using modular distance learning. The researcher utilized the descriptive method of research. There were 200 grade three pupils who acted as research participants. Data were collected using the self-made questionnaire checklist distributed among the Grade 3 pupil participants. Google Forms was used to monitor the learners' responses. Relevant data were analyzed, evaluated, and interpreted utilizing the average mean and the percentage score. Based on the result, the frequency distribution of the 1st quarter grades obtained by the Grade 3 Pupils from Section Amber to Section Pearl showed that only 2% got outstanding marks; 20% got very good grades, 46% were good, and 32% were fair. This implied that during modular distance learning was not such effective in the 1st quarter due to adjustments done by the learners. During the 2nd quarter, 47 out of 200 pupils obtained very good grades. However, there are 30 learners who obtained 80-88 grades, while only 8 of them got the grade of 75-79. There was a big difference in the grades obtained from the 1st quarter to the 2nd quarter due to the adjustments made by the learners. The result of the study would be utilized as a basis for crafting a school action plan that would enhance the function of the Kamustahan Program in pupils' performance.

Keywords: *performance, modular distance learning, school, action plan, Kamustahan program*

Introduction

The outbreak of COVID 19 doesn't block everyone to acquire knowledge and learn more. Definitely, it challenged the whole education sector to continue such crusade in education despite of the obstacles confronted for the past two years since the virus entered the country. The DepEd has already affirmed that quality will not suffer despite of the virus interference. Therefore, quality will always be the concern of education amidst the drastic changes happened in education. From face to face classes, every learner had tried each best to make adjustments on the new existing modality – the modular approach. In two years, it was proven that education still work, everyone could always dream of good education.

The Kamustahan program implemented by the DepEd Antipolo is of big boost in motivating learners in the new normal. Through this activity which is being done once a week or twice a month, depending on the teacher's most convenient time, the learners' performance may also increase particularly in Mathematics. The concern of every teacher to follow up every learners' performance task and other related activities could seemingly increase their level of performance. It motivates them to do more and show more of their finished tasks amidst the new normal.

The school has shown that pandemic is not a hindrance in achieving goals. It was manifested on the zero dropped out rate for the School Year 2020-2021. It only means that constant motivation may bring every school institution to success. Though distance learning presents incredible challenges and opportunities for teachers, parents and students. This year's changing circumstances call for great flexibility and resilience as learning moves from home to school and back again. Everyone's circumstances are different. More focused and independent learning from home is easier for some students and families than others.

This is the major reason on why the researcher conduct this study. She believes that despite of the pandemic brought by COVID 19, the learners don't stop doing their job to perform and excel. Any issue and result that would come out from the conduct of the study would be beneficial to strengthen the Kamustahan program of the school. This activity would help much in maintaining and keeping the confidence of every learner.

Galusha et. al (2006), especially considering that they have to spend twice as much time in preparing and delivering an online course as compared to a traditional course. With all of the challenges facing distance education, studies show that distance learning students desire content and motivational support beyond course materials and are limited in their success without it. Wang and Newlin (2000) point out that little is known about the characteristics of students in distance education courses. As a result, effective curriculum design is hindered by the lack of understanding of the characteristics, attitudes, and needs of the students in these courses. At the same time, the faculty needs to develop skills in helping students adjust to the unique features of distance education. However, the lack of adequate training may prevent them from fully participating in the distance education practices

Modular learning uses modules that facilitate student learning by themselves. It is a form of distance learning that uses Self-Learning Modules (SLM) based on the most essential learning competencies (MELCS) developed by the teachers with the aid of curriculum developers. Biggs (1999) explained that modular learning is the approach where the focus is on learning outcomes, and its success relies on connecting outcomes to student learning and course design. These areas combine to make a course constructively aligned as

discussed. The use of modules encourages independent study. One of the benefits of using modules for instruction is the acquisition of better self-study or learning skills among students. Students engage themselves in learning the concepts presented in the module.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance level of the selected Grade 3 participants in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. 1st quarter and 2nd quarter grade; and
 - 1.2. summative test results?
2. What are the issues/challenges met by the teacher in teaching Mathematics among the grade 3 pupils using the modular mode in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. pupils' participation rate; and
 - 2.2. Pupils' retention rate?
3. What is the effect of Kamustahan program among the grade 3 pupils in terms of :
 - 3.1 pupils' interest/motivation; and
 - 3.2 pupils' performance?
4. What output can be crafted from the result of the study?

Innovation, Intervention, and Strategy

A School Action Plan focusing on the enhancement of Kamustahan program among the grade 3 pupils will be one of the innovations of this study.

Methodology

Participants

The respondents of the study were selected purposively. These includes 200 total number of grade 3 pupils from Section Amber to Section Pearl.

Table 1. Total Number of Grade 3 Participants

Section	Male	Female	Total
Amber	5	5	10
Amethyst	5	5	10
Aquamarine	5	5	10
Beryl	5	5	10
Bronze	5	5	10
Carnelian	5	5	10
Chalcedony	5	5	10
Chrysolite	5	5	10
Crystal	5	5	10
Diamond	5	5	10
Emerald	5	5	10
Garnet	5	5	10
Gold	5	5	10
Ivory	5	5	10
Jade	5	5	10
Jasper	5	5	10
Moonstone	5	5	10
Olmen	5	5	10
Onyx	5	5	10
Pearl	5	5	10
Total	100	100	200

Procedure

Data were collected using the self-made questionnaire checklist distributed among the Grade 3 pupil participants. Google form was used to monitor the responses done by the learners. Relevant data were analysed, evaluated, and interpreted utilizing the average mean and the percentage score.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1: The performance level of the selected Grade 3 participants in terms of the following:

It could be gleaned from the table the frequency distribution of the 1st quarter grades obtained by the Grade 3 Pupils from Section Amber to Section Pearl. The data shows that only 2% got the outstanding mark; 20% got very good grades; 46% were good and 32% were fair. This implied that during modular distance learning was not such effective on the 1st quarter due to adjustments done by the learners.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of the 1st Quarter Grade of Grade 3 Pupils

Total	Outstanding 95-100	%	Very Good 89-94	%	Good 80-88	%	Fair 75-79	%
100	2	2%	20	20%	46	46%	32	32%

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of the 2nd Quarter Grade of Grade 3 Pupils

Total	Outstanding 95-100	%	Very Good 89-94	%	Good 80-88	%	Fair 75-79	%
100	15	15%	47	47%	30	30%	8	8%

Table 3 shows that out of 100 grade 3 pupils, 15 of them got the outstanding grades during the 2nd quarter while 47 obtained very good grades. However, there are 30 learners who obtained 80-88 grades while only 8 of them got the grade of 75-79. There was a big difference on the grades obtained from the 1st quarter to 2nd quarter due to the adjustments made by the learners.

Table 4. Mean Percentage Score of the Summative Test Results of Grade 3 Pupils

Total	Mean	MPS	90-100	%	No. of Pupils		75-79	%
					80-89	%		
100	56.85	86	15	15	65	65	20	20

Table 4 shows overall the Mean Percentage Score obtained by the Grade 3 Pupils during the modular distance learning. Out of 100 pupils, 15% of them got 90-100 percent; 65 of them got 80-89 percent and only 20 got 75-79 percent.

Problem 2: Issues/challenges met by the teacher in teaching Mathematics among the grade 3 pupils using the modular mode in terms of the following:

Table 5. Grade 3 Pupils' Percentage of Participation during the 1st and 2nd Modular Distance Learning

Total	First Quarter		Second Quarter	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
100	75.86	83.4	85.60	90.36

It could be gleaned from Table 5 the Percentage of Participation of the grade 3 pupils during the 1st and 2nd quarter of modular distance learning. According to the result, there was a big difference on the rate of participation among the male and female learners. One of the issues during the first quarter was the participation of the whole class in the modular learning modality. It was already remedied during the 2nd quarter among the male and female learners wherein an increase of 9.74 and 6.96 were recorded respectively.

Table 6. Grade 3 Pupils' Retention Rate during the 1st and 2nd Modular Distance Learning

Total	First Quarter		Second Quarter	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
100	100%	100%	98%	99%

The retention rate of the grade 3 pupils during the 1st quarter was 100% compared to the 2nd quarter which was 98% for male and 99% for female. Only 2 of the male grade 3 pupils dropped out of classes and only 1 female pupil dropped of the class during the second quarter. The challenge met by the teacher is to encourage the remaining 2% of the total number of learners during the second quarter. However, only 98% of the total number have sustained and retained in class. Retention rate is a measure of the proportion of students who continue their studies after their first quarter.

Problem 3: Effect of Kamustahan program among the grade 3 pupils in terms of:

Table 7. Number of Pupil Demonstrated Interest in Modular Distance Learning and After the Kamustahan Program

Total	Pre Kamustahan						Post Kamustahan					
	Male		Female		Total	%	Male		Female		Total	%
No.	%	No.	%	No.			%	No.	%	No.		
100	34	34%	36	36%	70	35	89	89%	93	93%	182	91%

The table above shows the difference in the number of Grade 3 pupils who demonstrated their interest in modular distance learning before and after the Kamustahan program conducted by the Grade 3 teachers. Out of 200 pupils, 35% showed their interest in modular distance learning during the Pre-Kumustahan Activity. However, during the post-kamustahan program, wherein the teachers applied

necessary strategies on MDL like home visits and regular talks with parents, 91% or an increase of 56% demonstrated their interest in the MDL approach.

According to the teacher advisers, some of the indicators that showed learners' interest in MDL are the following: regular early submission of outputs like LAS, worksheets and others; regular attendance during online kamustahan and increase in the performance level of pupils in Mathematics.

Table 8. Performance Level of the Grade 3 Pupils Using the Modular Learning

<i>Total</i>	<i>Outstanding</i> <i>95-100</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Very Good</i> <i>89-94</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Good</i> <i>80-88</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Fair</i> <i>75-79</i>	<i>%</i>
100	15	15%	47	47%	30	30%	8	8%

Table 8 shows that out of 100 grade 3 pupils, 15 of them got outstanding grades during the 2nd quarter while 47 obtained very good grades. However, 30 learners obtained 80-88 grades while only 8 of them got the grade of 75-79. There was a big difference on the grades obtained from the 1st quarter to the 2nd quarter due to the adjustments made by the learners.

Problem 4: Output can be crafted from the result of the study

A School Action Plan for An Enhanced Kamustahan Program is crafted by the researcher with the support of all grade 3 teachers and approved by the school head. The action plan will also determine the 100% involvement of learners in modular distance learning which is the positive effect of the Kamustahan program is.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded the following statements: (1) Modular distance learning is also as effective as in-person or face-to-face classes. (2) The grade 3 pupils have performed well using the MDL approach. (3) Parents are indispensable tools for the success of learners in their studies especially in this time of pandemic,

Below are the recommendations for the improvement of future researchers: (1) Kamustahan activity/program should be strengthened for the benefit of learners. (2) Teachers should craft their own action plan to enhance the kamustahan program. (3) Teachers should initiate innovations for the benefit of learners, especially during this pandemic times.

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